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ВПЛИВ ВІТАМІНУ D НА ПЕРЕБІГ БРОНХІАЛЬНОЇ АСТМИ (ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ)

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THE EFFECT OF VITAMIN D ON THE COURSE OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Анотація:

Бронхіальна астма є одним із найпоширеніших хронічних захворювань респіраторної системи, що характеризується запальними змінами, гіперреактивністю бронхів та рецидивуючими епізодами обструкції. В останні роки все більшу увагу приділяють ролі вітаміну D у регуляції імунних процесів, зокрема в патогенезі аутоімунних та алергічних захворювань. В нашій статті зазначено, що добавки вітаміну D мають позитивний вплив на зменшення частоти загострень бронхіальної астми та на параметри зовнішньої функції легень.

Abstract:

Bronchial asthma is one of the most common chronic diseases of the respiratory system, characterized by inflammatory changes, bronchial hyperreactivity and recurrent episodes of obstruction. In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the role of vitamin D in the regulation of immune processes, in particular in the pathogenesis of autoimmune and allergic diseases. Our article indicates that vitamin D supplements have a positive effect on reducing the frequency of exacerbations of bronchial asthma and on parameters of external lung function.

Ключові слова: бронхіальна астма, вітамін D, імунна система, дефіцит, добавки

Keywords: bronchial asthma, vitamin D, immune system, deficiency, supplements

The urgency of the problem. Bronchial asthma is a heterogeneous, autoimmune disease characterized by chronic airway inflammation, bronchial hyperreactivity, and reverse airflow obstruction, manifested by attacks of shortness of breath, coughing, wheezing, and chest tightness [1]. According to the estimates of the World Health Organization, AD affects about 300 million people in the world, and its prevalence continues to increase, which causes significant socio-economic losses. In the pathogenesis of bronchial asthma, a combination of genetic predisposition, environmental factors and individual characteristics of the body play a role [2, 3].

In recent decades, considerable attention has been paid to studying the role of vitamin D not only in maintaining calcium-phosphorus homeostasis, but also in regulating the immune response, inflammatory processes, and tissue remodeling. It is known that vitamin D receptors (VDR) are expressed on immunocompetent cells - T-lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes, macrophages and dendritic cells, which

indicates its involvement in the modulation of immune processes.

Vitamin D deficiency is considered as one of the potential risk factors for the development and severe course of bronchial asthma. According to numerous studies, a low level of 25(OH)D in blood serum is associated with an increased frequency of asthma exacerbations, a decrease in the effectiveness of inhaled corticosteroids, and an increase in the risk of infectious complications of the respiratory tract. At the same time, optimal levels of vitamin D can help reduce inflammatory activity, improve lung function, and control disease.

The question becomes especially relevant in the conditions of global vitamin D deficiency, which is common among different age groups and geographical regions, as well as in patients with chronic diseases of the respiratory system. Despite numerous studies, the mechanisms of the relationship between the level of vitamin D and the pathogenesis of bronchial asthma remain not fully elucidated. The impact of vitamin D

status on asthma phenotypes, immune pathways of Th1/Th2 regulation, cytokine synthesis, and response to basic therapy requires further study.

Thus, the study of the role of vitamin D in the formation, course and treatment of bronchial asthma is an actual direction of modern medicine, which is important both for understanding the pathogenetic mechanisms of the disease and for the development of personalized approaches to prevention and treatment. [1].

Materials and methods: we conducted a literature review based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. An analysis of current information on the effect of vitamin D on the course of bronchial asthma was carried out.

The purpose of our work was to analyze literary sources, research and determine the effect of vitamin D on the course of bronchial asthma.

Results and discussion: Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin that has two forms: cholecalciferol (vitamin D3) and ergocalciferol (vitamin D2) [4].

Deficiency of 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] is a common phenomenon in the world and is observed in different age groups and regions. Recent systematic estimates suggest a significant proportion of the population with 25(OH)D levels below commonly accepted thresholds (eg, <30 nmol/L and <50 nmol/L), with regional and seasonal variations. Such a high prevalence of D-deficiency creates prerequisites for its possible influence on the share of chronic inflammatory diseases, in particular, bronchial asthma.

According to the latest studies, vitamin D has significant immunomodulatory effects that suppress airway inflammation, reduce airway hyperreactivity, reduce glandular secretion, slow down the growth of bronchial smooth muscle cells, improve airway remodeling, enhance the body's response to corticosteroids, and reduce the number of bronchial asthma attacks [5].

Sun exposure is the main source of vitamin D in humans. Solar ultraviolet radiation photolyzes 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin to previtamin D3, which is then converted to vitamin D3 (cholecalciferol). Cholecalciferol from skin and food is hydroxylated in the liver to 25(OH)D and stored. Parathyroid hormone controls calcium phosphate homeostasis by regulating the hydroxylation of 25(OH)D to its biologically active form (1,25(OH)2D3) in the kidney. Vitamin D signaling primarily occurs through binding of 1,25(OH)2D3 to the vitamin D receptor, formation of a heterodimer with the retinoid X receptor, and subsequent regulation of gene expression by binding of this heterodimer to genomic sequences known as vitamin D response elements. Vitamin D, testify to the pleiotropic effects of vitamin D in humans [3].

The most well-known role of vitamin D is the regulation of metabolism and absorption of calcium and phosphorus by bones. However, the presence of the vitamin D receptor in other organs and tissues also indicates that the functions of vitamin D are not limited to mineral homeostasis and maintenance of the health of the musculoskeletal system. Vitamin D plays a

powerful role in other systems, including the immune system [2].

The vitamin D receptor is a transcription factor that affects the expression of thousands of genes. In addition to its role in mineral metabolism, it plays an important role in other functions, such as immune system functioning, glucose metabolism, and neurocognitive functions. Epithelial cells of the airways and immune cells in the lungs express the vitamin D receptor, and the regulatory mechanism of the activity of the enzyme 25(OH)D 1 α -hydroxylase in the lungs is different from that in the kidneys, which can lead to an increase in 1,25(OH)2D in the lungs, which leads to changes in immune regulation [6].

The effect of vitamin D on the course of bronchial asthma can be described by several mechanisms:

1. Immunomodulatory effect - Vitamin D regulates the balance between Th1 and Th2 lymphocytes, reducing Th2-dependent inflammation, which is characteristic of bronchial asthma. The secretion of interleukins (IL)-4, IL-5, IL-13, which are responsible for eosinophilic inflammation and IgE production, also decreases.

2. The anti-inflammatory effect is manifested in a decrease in the levels of cytokines IL-6 and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), which are involved in chronic bronchial inflammation. Also, vitamin D contributes to the maintenance of the epithelial barrier of the respiratory tract, reducing the permeability to allergens and pathogens [6,7].

In a large meta-analysis, it was found that the level of vitamin D in blood serum is positively correlated with parameters of lung function, such as forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) and forced vital capacity of the lungs (FVC), which are important parameters in the development of bronchial asthma [6].

The results of the review by the author Williamson A and co-authors confirm the role of vitamin D supplements or its hydroxylated metabolites in reducing the risk of exacerbations of bronchial asthma or improving the control of bronchial asthma [4].

Lower vitamin D levels have been hypothesized to correlate with increased total immunoglobulin E (IgE) and eosinophil counts [2].

Numerous cohort and case-control studies have shown an association between low 25(OH)D and more severe clinical manifestations of asthma: higher frequency of exacerbations, reduced disease control, lower expiratory function (FEV₁), and increased need for systemic corticosteroids. However, observational data do not provide a definitive conclusion about a causal relationship, since vitamin D deficiency may be a marker of concomitant factors (less physical activity, less time spent in the sun, concomitant comorbidities) that also affect the course of the disease.

A meta-analysis by Litonjua AA et al showed that vitamin D supplementation can prevent asthma exacerbations, especially in those patients with very low baseline vitamin D blood levels (25OHD < 10 ng/mL or 25 nmol/L) [8].

A meta-analysis by Fedora K et al showed that asthma exacerbations were significantly lower in the group of patients receiving vitamin D compared to the

placebo group. This review also found that although vitamin D can generally reduce the frequency of asthma exacerbations, the effect is more significant in patients treated with glucocorticosteroids compared with those not treated with glucocorticosteroids.

Both glucocorticosteroids and vitamin D can individually control the release of inflammatory chemokines in human airway smooth muscle, and vitamin D and glucocorticosteroids have also been shown to synergistically generate a tolerogenic phenotype of dendritic cells, which is critical for immunomodulation and reduced reactivity to self and foreign antigens [5].

Currently, no international guidelines (eg, GINA) recommend the routine administration of vitamin D to all patients with asthma as a standard part of disease management; however, the guidelines note interest in the role of D-status in specific situations and suggest potential benefit in patients with documented deficiency or frequent exacerbations. The clinical use of replacement therapy should be considered individually, taking into account the baseline 25(OH)D level, risks, and possible interactions with other treatment approaches.

Conclusion: the accumulated database indicates a biological basis for the effect of vitamin D on immune processes in the respiratory tract and the association of low 25(OH)D with severe asthma. Interventional studies show the potential of treatment in the prevention of some exacerbations, especially in patients with deficiency, but unequivocal recommendations for widespread clinical use are not yet available. Further randomized trials with clear stratification by D-status, asthma phenotypes, and standardized endpoints are needed to inform practice guidelines.

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